

General Concepts of “Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning”

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Abstract: Long ago, there was all kinds of work which was only done by the humans. There were no such machines and technologies like today. At that time, science was not developed and technologies were not invented. So the working is totally dependent on the peoples and humans have recognised that “Today’s science is the tomorrow’s technology”. New superiorly advanced technologies are not less than the blessing of god. Adaptive inventions for reducing human work and a bright future were invented which is simply called Artificial Intelligence and Machine learning. Even though there were many false assumptions at the early beginning, we are witnessing a new era of errorless technology and superior science. This review involves the general concepts of artificial intelligence and machine learning.

Keywords: Digitalization, reasoning, general AI, supervised learning, unsupervised learning, humanoids.

I. INTRODUCTION

As the humans have proved their presence on the earth, it is important that every individual should understand what artificial intelligence and machine learning is going to mean for the human race. As a nice poem summarized by W. H. Auden which gives the relationship between human life and robotics:

Those who will not reason
Perish in the act;
Those who will not act
Perish for that reason.

The poem explains that “Fittest survival” i.e. only those humans/machines will survive who prove their existence by their best performance, high intelligence and maximum capacity. Hence it’s high time and precipice of one of the most magnificent discoveries of supremacy since man learnt to create tools and fire. It is a road that once we walk ahead; there will be no turning back, once we achieve machine super intelligence which will be self learning, completely automatic and self-improving.

As we see any sci-fi movie like iron man, star wars, terminator etc. which vary in completely equipped super hero’s to the world destroying super robots. Even if anyone has seen missile or space shuttle launching, automatically driven cars, or simple robots which help in household chores to hard power full muscle works, which are very great examples of human intelligence. No doubt that artificial intelligence and machine learning are the two hottest buzzwords all over the world right now, and often seem to be used interchangeably.

II. RELATED WORK

Peter Norvig and Stuart Russell [1] in their research paper “Artificial intelligence: A modern approach” have implemented the basic perspectives of artificial intelligence. They concluded that artificial intelligence is a combination of reasoning, learning, perception, linguistic approach and problem solving. Niklas Lavesson[3] also has described the supervised type of machine learning .The ambition of this review is to introduce the types

of machine learning such as supervised, unsupervised and reinforcement etc. The review also explores the applications of AI and machine learning in real time.

George F Ludger [10] who described structures and strategies for artificial intelligence. The review also contains the methodologies of artificial intelligence such as weak artificial intelligence and strong artificial intelligence. It also considers the current real world applications and current processes in artificial intelligence.

III. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI)

According to the father of artificial intelligence John McCarthy, who coined the term “Artificial intelligence” in 1956, said that “It is the combination of science and engineering to make intelligent devices for human welfare.”

“Artificial intelligence is an intellect [13] that is much smarter than the best human brain in practically every field, including computer science and linguistic logic.” It is a modern method of machines which will do muscle work and illustrate complex questions in an “intellectual” manner. It is concerned with the basic and most important aspects in our life i.e. philosophy, computer science, mathematics, linguistics, biology, neuron science, sociology etc. AI plays a very important role to exhibit intelligent behavior, to learn, demonstrate and give advice to the user.

Artificial General Intelligence or AGI is a system that defines that the machine can do intellectual behavior as the humans can do many processes at a time. A broader view to artificial intelligence is that it can be the combination of learning, perception, problem solving and adapting new solutions to the system. It also involves linguistic logic and reasoning [1].

Artificial intelligence has 2 types:

1. Weak AI.
2. Strong AI.

Fig. I. A Diagram of sectors in AI

1. Weak AI:

The principle of Weak AI is that the machines behave as if they are intelligent. Weak AI proves that virtual abilities like thinking, talking, moving can be done by machine if they are programmed in that manner. E.g. In the chess game, the computer can play and move players automatically. The computer does not have thinking ability but in actual it is programmed so that the computer always takes the right step.

2. Strong AI:

The principle of Strong AI is that the machines will do calculations and think for themselves and will predict the answer in future. E.g. The artificial intellectual supercomputer „WATSON“ invented by IBM. Thus in future, there will definitely be such machines or maybe humanoids which will do its own work and think more powerful than human beings.

IV. MACHINE LEARNING

Machine learning is a current application of AI which promotes the reality of being able to give machines the access to data for more ease in human work and just to learn them for

themselves. Learning [2] is a key hallmark of artificial intelligence. It is an ability of the machines to take real – time data and feedback and improves performance over a time. Machine learning is a type of artificial intelligence which has the ability to learn and takes the data to get good output. Both the terms Artificial intelligence and machine learning are combined very frequently when concepts like big data, data science and analysis come to mind. Machine learning is a very efficient solution to handle such big data in multinational industries. They actually work like a super-computer. These machines or generally known as “Humanoids” are very perfect at their work. These robots/machines can talk, answer complex questions, and multiple jobs at a time.

Fig.II. Diagram representing machine learning mechanism

The diagram explains that machine learning not only depends on how the knowledge engineer performs on training bases but also how he works for new experiments. Machine learning is one of the most important technical approaches to AI and the basis of many recent advances and commercial applications of AI. Modern machine learning is a statistical process that helps to define the output and future use of data [3]. There are following types of learning:

1. Supervised learning.
2. Unsupervised/predictive learning.
3. Reinforcement learning.

1. Supervised learning:

Fig. III. Supervised learning model

In this process, if the researchers tell the machine what the correct answer is for a particular input. It is the most common technique for training neural networks [4] and other machine learning architectures. It involves learning a mapping from a set of inputs to a target variable. The target is discrete and real value. It is solved by decision trees, native trees [5], boosting and multi-layer [6] neural networks.

2. Unsupervised/predictive learning:

In this method, no labels are given to the learning algorithm, leaving it on its own to find structure in its input. It can be a goal in itself i.e. hidden pattern[7] and data. Researchers don't know what to do at this moment, research is still going on. No target variables are provided. It is solved by grouping into K groups.

Fig.IV. Unsupervised learning model

3. Reinforcement learning:

In this algorithm, The AI ‘agent’[8] decides how to behave in order to get most of the work done. A computer program interacts with a dynamic environment in which it must perform a certain task to win against an opponent. The program gives feedback in terms of punishment or reward. The machine itself selects actions to be performed for better output.

V. Methodology

Our literature review followed a systematic and structured approach to ensure the validity and reliability of the findings. We acknowledge the importance of a rigorous methodology in conducting a literature review. Our study employed a systematic approach, including research question formulation, comprehensive data collection, inclusion and exclusion criteria, data analysis, critical evaluation of sources, and synthesis of findings. By following these methodological steps, we aimed to minimize biases and ensure the

scientific rigor of our review. Systematic literature review method was used over the multivocal literature review and other review methods for three reasons- a) high objectivity than other narrative methods b) results are more conclusive and replicable with a clear process of selecting literature and c) helps to identify research gaps. Therefore, SLR helps to advance a research field with more clarity of past studies and projecting future research agendas [50]. We believe that our approach provides a robust foundation for the analysis presented in the manuscript. The key steps of our methodology are as follows:

Research Question Formulation: The first step in our literature review process was to formulate a clear research question to guide our study. The research question focused on understanding the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on the business industry, including its applications, trends, challenges, and potential future developments.

Comprehensive Data Collection: To ensure inclusivity and comprehensiveness, we conducted an extensive search of reputable academic databases, such as PubMed, IEEE Xplore, Google Scholar, and Scopus. The search was limited to peer-reviewed articles between 2015 and 2023, conference papers, and reports published between 2017 and 2023 to capture the most recent and relevant literature.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: We established specific inclusion and exclusion criteria to select relevant publications for our review. Inclusion criteria involved publications directly related to the impact of AI in business, while exclusion criteria excluded

articles that were in non-English languages and did not meet the thematic focus or lacked academic rigor.

Data Analysis and Synthesis: Following data collection, we systematically analyzed the selected articles to identify key themes, trends, and findings. The analysis involved coding and categorizing the literature based on the different aspects of AI in business, such as applications, challenges, and trends.

Critical Evaluation and Quality Assessment: To ensure the quality of the literature included in the review, we critically evaluated each selected publication. We assessed the credibility of the

sources, the validity of research methodologies used, and the relevance of the findings to our research question as shown in figure 5.

Synthesis and Dissemination of Findings: The findings from the reviewed literature were synthesized and organized into a coherent and logical narrative. We provided a comprehensive overview of the impact of AI in business, addressing its various applications, challenges, current trends, and potential future developments. The results were presented in a structured manner in the manuscript. We discuss the application areas of AI in business, in section 5.

Fig.V. Flow chart for screening and selection of articles

VI. APPLICATIONS OF AI AND MACHINE LEARNING

As we know how AI is the most useful topic in the

human life. There are many day-to-day examples of AI. There is Siri by apple, google now by google, Watson by IBM and cortana by windows mobile for various operating systems

which are intelligent digital personal assistants [9] which have speech and gesture recognition systems which help the user to find and sort out all the needed things without any physical appearance.

It will give all the information to you like “where is the nearest restaurant/college/bus station?” or it will remind you of your pending work, alarm clock, personal information as well as your friend’s birthday or important meetings to handle, etc.

Fig.VI. Siri by Apple

Fig.VII. Watson by IBM

Many future and current researches are going on by scientists on humanoids i.e. robotics along with human behavior and feelings. There are also high performance cars along with automatic driver assists, missiles with radar, satellites and navigation systems.

The self-driving car called ‘Waymo’ [11] which is a google initiative drives on the road without a driver. Again NASA and GOOGLE are working together for the first ever humanoid astronaut known as ‘Valkyrine’ [12] which is an absolute example of artificial intelligence.

Fig.VIII. Cortana by Microsoft

According to a review article by Haleem et al. [51], AI is gaining popularity in the business industry due to its potential to transform various areas such as customer service, marketing, finance, healthcare, manufacturing, logistics, and human resources. AI can automate tasks, analyze data, and provide insights, enabling businesses to improve decision-making, increase efficiency, and enhance the customer experience [51, 52]. AI is transforming customer service by enabling chatbots and virtual assistants to handle routine customer queries and provide personalized recommendations to customers [53, 54]. AI-powered sentiment analysis can also help businesses understand customer feedback and respond to complaints in real-time. AI can be used to optimize marketing campaigns, personalize content, and predict consumer behavior [55, 56]. AI algorithms can analyze

consumer data to create targeted marketing campaigns that deliver the right message to the right audience at the right time [35, 57]. Moreover, AI-powered chatbots can engage with customers in real-time, helping businesses improve the customer experience. AI can automate repetitive tasks, such as data entry and reconciliation, enabling finance and accounting professionals to focus on higher-value tasks [58]. AI algorithms can also analyze financial data to identify fraud and prevent financial crimes. Moreover, AI-powered portfolio management and algorithmic trading can help financial institutions make better investment decisions. AI is revolutionizing healthcare by enabling personalized medicine, drug discovery, and patient monitoring [59, 60]. Moreover, AI-powered diagnosis and treatment can help healthcare professionals make more accurate and timely diagnoses and improve patient outcomes [61].

AI can improve efficiency and productivity in manufacturing by enabling predictive maintenance, quality control, and supply chain optimization [62, 63]. AI algorithms can analyze sensor data to predict machine failure, enabling manufacturers to perform maintenance before breakdowns occur [64]. Moreover, AI-powered

autonomous robots can help with repetitive tasks, enabling manufacturers to free up human resources for more complex tasks. AI

can optimize logistics and supply chains by enabling real-time tracking and delivery prediction, as well as inventory management and demand forecasting [36, 65]. Moreover, AI-powered chatbots can provide customers with real-time updates on their deliveries, improving customer experience.

AI can help businesses with human resources tasks such as candidate screening, employee engagement, performance management, and talent management [66, 67]. AI algorithms can analyze employee data to identify patterns and make predictions about employee performance and attrition. Moreover, AI-powered chatbots can help with routine HR queries, freeing up HR professionals for more complex tasks.

Table 1 shows some of the reviewed articles on the different functions of business, where AI has the potential to be integrated and provide ease of service and convenience to the stakeholders.

Business Area	Objectives of the study	References
Marketing and Sales	Personalized recommendations, predictive analytics, chatbots, and sentiment analysis	[35, 68]
	Marketing Automation, neuromarketing, viral marketing, voice recognition, and conversion optimization,	[20, 69, 70]
	Efficiency improvements, accuracy improvements, better decision-making, customer relationship improvements, sales increases, cost reductions, and risk reductions	[5, 34, 71]
	Predict customer behavior, one-to-one digital marketing, enhance sales, and increase customer satisfaction.	[48, 49, 72]
	Consumers' perception and voice-assisted AI centers	[51, 73]
	Knowledge creation and knowledge management in B2B sales	[74]

	Social media and digital advertising	[21, 57, 75]
Finance	Fraud detection, risk assessment, portfolio management, and algorithmic trading	[37, 38, 76]
	Lending Risk, security in processing payments, automating compliance-related work, and improving customer targeting.	[58, 77]
	Digital financial inclusion, risk detection, information asymmetry, availing customer support and helpdesk through chatbots, and fraud detection	[78]
	Digital servitization	[79]
	Ethical implications	[80]
	Stable functioning and sustainable growth	[81]
	Portfolio diversification.	[82]
Healthcare	Diagnosis and treatment, drug discovery, personalized medicine, patient monitoring	[6, 59, 61, 83]
	Ethical risks presented by AI in health	[84]
	Data infrastructure	[85]
	Diagnosis, patient morbidity or mortality risk assessment, disease outbreak prediction and surveillance, and health policy and planning.	[86]
	Ethical challenges: informed consent to use, safety and transparency, algorithmic fairness and biases, and data privacy.	[61, 87]
	Diagnosis and treatment recommendations, patient engagement and adherence, and administrative activities.	[61, 88]
	Medical, legal, ethical, and societal questions	[89]
Manufacturing	Challenges for AI startups- clinical limitations, credibility, model explainability, non-clinical stakeholder, management, technical depth	[90]
	Predictive maintenance, quality control, supply chain optimization, and autonomous robots	[36, 62, 65, 90]
	Camera calibration, detection, tracking, camera position and orientation (pose) estimation, inverse rendering, procedure storage, virtual object creation, registration, and rendering	[63, 76]
	Data-driven predictive analytics and decision-making in highly complex	[39]
	Efficient and intelligent automation	[7, 65, 66]
	Timely acquisition, distribution, and utilization of real-time data	[63, 64]
	Virtual manufacturing	[65, 69]
Human Resources	Informed deep learning, explainable AI, domain adaptation, active learning, multi-task learning, and graph neural networks	[79]
	Candidate screening, employee engagement, performance management, and talent management	[67, 89]
	Job replacement, human-robot/AI collaboration, decision-making and learning opportunities, and HRM activities, namely, recruiting, training and job performance.	[67, 88]
	Complexity of HR phenomena, constraints imposed by small data sets, ethical questions associated with fairness and legal constraints, and employee reaction to management via database-driven algorithms	[66, 76]
	Interaction of artificial intelligence (AI) (primarily robots) and human workers	[9, 11]
Recruitment and performance management	[9, 66]	

Table 1: Summary of the articles reviewed of the following business areas of AI.

VII. CONCLUSION

The entire world is on the way to Digitalization and for that purpose artificial intelligence and machine learning concepts plays an important role. Our research paper is totally based upon how intelligence and new machine technologies get invented in our day to day life. Today's machines are ready to give knowledge based education and are responsible for improving intelligence. In the future, we don't think and imagine about the progress of the world due to only Artificial Intelligence and Innovative Machines. We can't imagine what is happening in the surrounding world because of scientists and engineers. Scientists developed the Robots that work like a Human beings and the research is going on to create the best world in the future. Youth generation support is one of the most important parts to develop the new technologies. Combination of Science and Engineering and the quality machine learning will surely take the world at its highest fit.

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